

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MANENGU****FIRST NAME: CASIMIR****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA****Formatted:** Font: 10 pt**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What are the basic steps to be taken in writing an academic essay?

- Understanding the topic, reading and researching what to write, getting the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis, and answering the questions on what is known about the topic. Is this material useful to the topic/argument?
- Start writing an essay from the beginning with the introduction, the body, and the conclusion.
- The steps required to be undertaken before starting the essay are early start-up, defining the question and analyzing the task, and**

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drafting an initial plan including the initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic.¹

- The first step is to produce a comprehensive draft according to the structure and framework of the essay as a raw material refined through editing and redrafting.

2. What is the importance of the style guide for the writer?

- A style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of writing that will ensure consistency in written output.²**
- A style is just the correct **punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary usage.**
- A style guideline is published to allow an author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece carries the **writer's personal style.**
- Many creative writers eschew the need for a style guide, believing that the ability to follow a standard English writing style should be an innate quality for any writer.

3. In author-date citations, a source by placing a parenthetical citation:

- Date, author, relevant page numbers, text.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7-10.

² Ibid., 40-42.

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Author, date, relevant page numbers.³

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4. What is distinguishing Pure and Applied Research?

Pure research is common in academic fields such as business, engineering, and medicine and in companies and government agencies that research to understand what must be known before they can solve a problem.

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Pure research addresses a conceptual problem that has any direct practical consequences. Applied research addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences; it improves the understanding of a community of researchers.

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Applied research addresses a community problem that does have practical consequences. Pure research addresses a conceptual problem with no direct practical consequences.

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Pure research addresses a conceptual problem that does not have any direct practical consequences; it only improves the

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³ [Kate L. Turabian](#), *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 141–142.

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understanding of a community of researchers. Applied research addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.⁴

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5. What includes the methodology as part of the research development?

The methodology includes an introduction and overview, the research design, an overview of the information needed, data collection methods or tools, data Analysis and synthesis, ethical considerations, issues of trustworthiness, limitations and delimitations, and a Chapter Summary.⁵

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The methodology briefly describes the introduction and overview, the research design, the information needed and sources of data, a proposed research sample, and findings.

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The methodology includes an introduction and overview, information needed and sources of data, plans and methods for data collection and data analysis, and a rationale for the methods to be used.

⁴ Ibid., 29–30.

⁵ Ibid., 435-438.

- The methodology includes the research design, the information needed and sources of data, a proposed research sample, plans and methods for data collection, and data analysis.

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6. **What is the data analysis process in the qualitative research?**

- The data analysis process begins with putting in place a plan to manage some data collected to identify patterns and construct a framework for communicating the essence of what the data revealed, given the purpose of the study.

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- The data analysis process depends only on the nature of the data collected, findings, and certain fundamental steps to be trustworthy (credible and dependable)

- The process data analysis begins with putting in place a plan to manage the large volume of data collected, identify significant patterns, and construct a framework for communicating the essence of what the data revealed, given the purpose of the study.

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- The process of data analysis begins with putting in place a plan to manage the large volume of data collected and reducing it in a meaningful way to identify significant patterns and construct a

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framework for communicating the essence of what the data revealed, given the purpose of the study.⁶

7. What is the preference for referencing using the WHO style?

The Harvard system referencing is preferred for the WHO technical report.

Numerical referencing is the preferred system for WHO publications and is obligatory for WHO technical reports.⁷

Both Harvard and numerical referencing can be combined in the same Product using the WHO style.

Numerical referencing is the system in WHO publications for the WHO publication.

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8. What is the order of dissertation chapters in scientific research?

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Introduction, literature review, methodology and research approach, findings, analysis, interpretation, synthesis, epilogue, afterword or final thoughts, conclusions, and recommendations.

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⁶ Turabian, 464-466.

⁷ World Health Organization. 2013. *WHO Style Guide*. Second edition. World Health Organization, 42-43.

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Introduction, literature review, methodology and research approach, findings, analysis, interpretation, synthesis, conclusions and recommendations, epilogue, afterword, or final Thoughts.⁸

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9. How is Zotero used for citation management?

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A citation management program helps to collect and organize references from different sources to be added only manually.

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A citation management program helps to collect and organize references from different sources to be added manually, with the identifier or using the Zotero connector.⁹

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⁸ Turabian, 73.

⁹ Turabian, 145.

- As citation management program helps to, collect and organize references from different sources to be added only using the Zotero connector

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10. How should a single author or editor be presented in the note when citing sources?

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- ##.Editor's Last Name, Editor's First Name, ed. Title of Book . . .
- ##. Author's First and Last Names, *Title of Book: Subtitle of Book* (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), XX.¹⁰
- ##.Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. *Title of Book: Subtitle of Book*. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication.
- ##. Editor's First and Last Names, ed., *Title of Book* . . .

¹⁰ Turabian, 149-150 .

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Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.